

Few-Shot Learning for Relevance Classification of Textual Social Media Posts in Disaster Response

David Hanny¹

¹IT:U Interdisciplinary Transformation University, Linz, Austria, ²Department of Geoinformatics - Z_GIS, Paris-Lodron-University Salzburg, Salzburg, Austria, ³Center for Geographic Analysis, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA, USA

Abstract

Social media can provide real-time insights during natural disasters, yet efficiently identifying relevant content remains a challenge due to the reliance on large labelled datasets and high computational costs. This study therefore investigates the potential of Few-Shot Learning (FSL) for relevance classification of textual social media posts during disasters. We compare few-shot prompting using eight Small Language Models (SLMs) and a contrastive learning approach (SetFit) with data from five disasters across the world: the 2020 California wildfires, 2021 Ahr Valley floods, 2023 Chile wildfires, 2023 Emilia-Romagna floods, and 2023 Turkey/Syria earthquake. GPT-4o-mini achieves the highest average macro F1 score (0.77) using just five labelled examples per class, while the multilingual-e5-base model fine-tuned with SetFit offers a strong alternative (avg. macro F1 = 0.65) without reliance on prompt engineering. Our findings highlight the potential of SLMs and FSL for scalable and resource-efficient data analytics in disaster management and broader social science research.

Keywords: *social media; few-shot learning; small language models; big data; machine learning; disaster management.*

1. Introduction

Social media data has become an established resource for real-time, crowd-sourced information during natural disasters, aiding both emergency response and recovery (Z. Wang & Ye, 2018). However, the vast and noisy nature of such data necessitates efficient methods to identify relevant information. Supervised learning approaches relies on large labelled datasets, which are difficult to obtain in natural disasters scenarios (Shah et al., 2021). Few-Shot Learning (FSL) can address such data scarcity by enabling Artificial Intelligence (AI) models to generalise from minimal labelled examples, reducing reliance on extensive annotation. Recently, techniques like in-context learning and contrastive learning (Y. Wang et al., 2020) have significantly advanced the adaptability of FSL. Regardless, its application in social media analysis, and particularly in disaster relevance classification, remains underexplored.

This study investigates the potential of FSL for identifying relevant disaster-related textual social media posts across five natural disasters. We compare few-shot prompting (Brown et al., 2020) with contrastive learning using SetFit (Tunstall et al., 2022), analysing their effectiveness across multiple use cases and languages. Given the computational constraints during disasters, we focus on Small Language Models (SLMs) with fewer than 10 billion parameters, which are feasible for local deployment (F. Wang et al., 2024). Our central research question is: *How does few-shot prompting on SLMs compare to prompt-free FSL with SetFit for relevance classification of textual social media posts?*

2. Related Work

Defining what content is relevant for effective emergency response during natural disasters is complex. Kaufhold et al. (2020) conceptualised relevance as a binary concept based on abstract (necessity, topicality) and factual (geographic, temporal distance) criteria, while Agarwal and Yiliyasi (2010) framed it as task-specific usefulness. Others refined this into multi-class classifications, distinguishing between levels of informativeness for disaster management (Blomeier et al., 2024; Olteanu et al., 2015).

Previous works in relevance classification used keyword filtering and tf-idf representations with random forests and Support Vector Machines (SVMs) (Habdank et al., 2017; Kaufhold et al., 2020; Olteanu et al., 2015). More recent studies favour deep learning, including CNNs (Huang et al., 2020) or transformer-based architectures like Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) (Madichetty et al., 2021). Blomeier et al. (2024) found that BERT outperformed other models in German-language tweet classification, achieving an accuracy of 0.71 in contrast to 0.51 for the best alternative. However, the training of such supervised machine learning models usually requires a significant amount of annotated training data. FSL addresses this challenge by enabling classification with minimal labelled data. Prompt-based in-context learning with generative AI models like Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT)

3 (Brown et al., 2020) and contrastive learning techniques such as SetFit (Tunstall et al., 2022) have achieved competitive results, with SetFit matching the performance of models fine-tuned on 20,000 examples using just 8 per class. Despite these advances, FSL remains underexplored in social media analysis. This study is the first to apply FSL for relevance classification of social media posts, covering multiple languages, geographic regions and types of natural disasters.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Data

We compiled a diverse dataset covering five natural disasters: (1) 2020 California wildfires, (2) 2021 Ahr Valley floods, (3) 2023 Chile wildfires, (4) 2023 Emilia-Romagna floods, and (5) 2023 Turkey/Syria earthquake. Using the former Twitter (X) v1.1 and v2 Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), we filtered for posts based on geographic location (nearby the disaster’s main impact sites) and event timelines (within several weeks of the event), yielding between 13,023 and 34,678,576 geo-referenced posts per use case. The primary languages were English, German, Italian, Spanish and Turkish.

To create our test data, we used a three-class scheme analogous to Olteanu et al. (2015) consisting of the following three relevance classes:

- **Related and relevant:** A post that is related to the respective natural disaster and relevant for emergency responders. It contains useful information for supporting disaster management (e.g. posts about destructions, in-situ information, critical infrastructure, affected individuals, affected areas, requests for help, caution or advice).
- **Related but not relevant:** A post that refers to the respective disaster but does not contain helpful or valuable information for supporting disaster management (e.g. declarations of solidarity, volunteering initiatives, appeals for donations, political or religious statements, bot-generated content, comparisons to past events, shared news articles).
- **Not related:** A post that has no relation to the disaster event in question.

As a large part of the posts in the raw data were unrelated to the disaster, we used the Disaster-Twitter-XLM-RoBERTa-AL model by Hanny et al. (2024) to ensure a balanced evaluation dataset. We extracted $\leq 10,000$ posts per use case such that 67% were disaster-related and 33% were not disaster-related. This preliminary subset consisted of 37,826 posts. Subsequently, we conducted an initial round of few-shot labelling with GPT-4o-mini, using few-shot prompting with five posts per class to categorise each post into one of our three relevance categories. Lastly, we drew a sample of ≤ 350 posts for each class per use case, resulting in an evaluation

dataset of size 4,746. As part of this effort, each post was pre-processed by replacing usernames and links with standardised tokens to avoid overfitting on specific users and external information from links.

Next, each post was annotated based on textual content using a consensus-based labelling approach with three human annotators. All of them were researchers in Geoinformatics with knowledge in disaster management and thus considered experts in the field. For label validity, an inter-annotator agreement of 100% was required. In addition, posts mentioning disasters outside the predefined set of events were excluded to ensure data consistency. The final evaluation set consisted of 4,577 posts: 1,631 annotated as *Not related*, 1,720 annotated as *Related but not relevant* and 1,226 annotated as *Related and relevant*.

3.2. Classification

For classification, we first considered **few-shot prompting** which represents a form of in-context learning (Dong et al., 2024) where the models receives textual instructions with additional examples. It does not require any fine-tuning and can be applied on top of any instruction-based generative Language Model (LM). In our case, we used five representative examples per class and provided the model with additional context from our labelling guide comparable to the definitions above. The prompt is depicted in Figure 1. We used this prompting technique with a total of eight state-of-the-art SLMs: GPT-4o-mini, Llama3.2 3B, Llama3.1 8B, Mistral 7B, Gemma2 9B and 2B, Phi3-mini and Qwen2.5 7B. Each can effectively be run on a local computer or, in the case of GPT-4o-mini, offers a highly cost-efficient API at 0.15\$ per million input tokens and 0.60\$ per million output tokens (as of February 2025).

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Your job is to classify tweets in the three categories "Related and relevant", "Related but not relevant", and "Not related" in the context of natural disasters (floods, wildfires and earthquakes). The categories are as follows:
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- "Related and relevant": The tweet contains helpful and valuable information for supporting disaster management (e.g. posts referring to destructions, in-situ information, critical infrastructure, affected individuals, affected areas, requests for help or caution and advice)
- "Related but not relevant": The tweet refers to the natural disaster but does not contain helpful or valuable information for supporting disaster management (e.g. declarations of solidarity, volunteering initiatives, appeals for donations, political or religious statements, bot-generated content, comparisons to past events, shared news articles)
- "Not related": The tweet has no relation to the natural disaster event.

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Here are some examples:
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- Tweet: "Here the entire street is under water. Water higher than the curb and the car entrance. The cellars are probably full too. #unwetter #cologne #bickendorf"
Label: "Related and relevant"

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... <five examples per class> ...  
Tweet: <post>  
Label:
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Figure 1: Prompt used for few-shot classification. <post> defines a placeholder for the content.

Second, we considered **SetFit** as a prompt-free alternative. The method fine-tunes a sentence transformers model using contrastive learning with a logistic regression classification head on

top (Tunstall et al., 2022). We used the same five training examples as in the few-shot prompting approach and fine-tuned a multilingual-e5-base model (L. Wang et al., 2024) for 10 epochs with batch size 32.

In our experiments, we always used posts in their original language to avoid any potential loss of information during translation (Cohn-Gordon & Goodman, 2019). To evaluate model performance, we computed standard classification metrics like accuracy, precision, recall and the F1-score for each model individually, both per use case and class, using a one-vs-all strategy for the multiclass setup. Posts for which one of the AI models produced invalid labels were excluded from the analysis to ensure consistency.

4. Results

Mistral 7B was unable to classify 9 posts and Phi3-mini could not categorise 6 posts. All other models returned valid labels for all data points. Figure 2 presents the accuracy and macro F1 scores for each model across all five use cases. GPT-4o-mini achieved the highest overall performance, with an average macro F1 score of 0.77. Its lowest performance was on the California wildfires dataset (macro F1 = 0.69), while it performed best on the Turkey/Syria earthquake dataset (macro F1 = 0.83). The second-best model, Qwen2.5 7B, achieved an average macro F1 score of 0.69, followed by SetFit with 0.65. The remaining models performed notably worse, with overall performance decreasing as model size decreased. The weakest model was Llama3.2 3B, which reached an average macro F1 score of 0.37 across all use cases.

Figure 2: Distribution of evaluation metrics for each model across our five use case scenarios.

The *Not related* class had the highest average precision (0.94) but a low recall (0.47), indicating that many instances were missed. The *Related but not relevant* class exhibited more balanced performance, with an average precision of 0.55 and recall of 0.58. The *Related and relevant* class showed a high recall (0.79) but lower precision (0.52), suggesting that while most relevant

instances were identified, there were also many false positives. In terms of use cases, the Ahr Valley floods dataset was classified best, with an average macro F1 score of 0.64 across models. The Italy floods use case followed closely, with an average macro F1 score of 0.61. The Turkey/Syria earthquake and California wildfires datasets had average macro F1 scores of 0.59 and 0.57, respectively. The Chile wildfire dataset was the most challenging, with the lowest overall classification performance (avg. macro F1 = 0.53).

Since our raw data was geo-referenced, we could also analyse model performance from a geospatial perspective. However, we did not identify any clear spatial patterns regarding classification accuracy for either model. The average accuracy was distributed similarly across geographic space, and there was no strong relationship between accuracy and proximity to affected areas.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

Our findings underscore the potential of few-shot learning for rapid deployment in disaster response scenarios. Notably, GPT-4o-mini, when paired with few-shot prompting, achieved high accuracy across all evaluated disaster events. However, its performance was consistently lowest for the English-language California wildfire data. The same trend could also be observed for Qwen2.5 7B and SetFit. This suggests that language is not the primary limiting factor in classification performance. Instead, the reduced accuracy for wildfire events might be linked to their complexity. Wildfires often occur scattered in geographically remote areas and tend to develop over extended periods. Additionally, it was difficult to distinguish mentions of wildfires and house fires during human annotation, indicating a degree semantic ambiguity of textual cues in wildfire-related social media data. Multilingual-e5-base, despite having only 278M parameters, was the third-best model when fine-tuned with SetFit, performing nearly as well as Qwen2.5 7B while using just 4% of the parameters. This highlights the efficiency of encoder-based models over instruction-based encoder-decoder architectures.

A key limitation of our methodology was the restricted number of evaluated methods, as only few-shot prompting and SetFit were tested. However, given SetFit's strong performance, we expect that FSL approaches like T-Few (Liu et al., 2022) should yield similar results. Another challenge is the stochastic nature of LM outputs, which can lead to inconsistencies in classification. In our experiments, this issue was highlighted by the fact that GPT-4o-mini and Qwen2.5 7B were the only models that consistently adhered to the specified label formats. While larger models likely improve few-shot performance, their high computational cost limits practical adoption in crisis scenarios. Notably, the true size of GPT-4o-mini remains undisclosed, albeit it is reportedly comparable to Llama3 8B (Zeff, 2024). Therefore, we cannot rule out that our evaluation might be somewhat unfair. Furthermore, we attempted to evaluate Deepseek-R1 7B as a reasoning model of comparable size. However, it exhibited prolonged

reasoning times, getting stuck on a single post for hours, which renders it impractical for timely crisis response applications.

Overall, this study demonstrates the effectiveness of FSL combined with SLMs for relevance classification of social media posts during disasters, emphasising the potential of these methods within the larger scope of the social sciences. Using only 15 labelled examples and minimal computational resources, we achieved a macro F1 score of 0.77 on a dataset of size 4,577 with GPT-4o and few-shot prompting. Alternative open-source models like Qwen2.5 7B and multilingual-e5-base fine-tuned with SetFit followed closely. These findings suggest that FSL can play a crucial role in efficiently identifying relevant content in large-scale internet data, making it a valuable tool for real-time analysis in disaster response and beyond.

This research has received funding from the European Commission - European Union under grant agreement 101093003 (HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-01).

References

- Agarwal, N., & Yiliyasi, Y. (2010). Information quality challenges in social media. *ICIQ*.
- Blomeier, E., Schmidt, S., & Resch, B. (2024). Drowning in the Information Flood: Machine-Learning-Based Relevance Classification of Flood-Related Tweets for Disaster Management. *Information*, 15(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info15030149>
- Brown, T., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J. D., Dhariwal, P., Neelakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Agarwal, S., Herbert-Voss, A., Krueger, G., Henighan, T., Child, R., Ramesh, A., Ziegler, D., Wu, J., Winter, C., ... Amodei, D. (2020). Language Models are Few-Shot Learners. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33, 1877–1901.
- Cohn-Gordon, R., & Goodman, N. (2019). *Lost in Machine Translation: A Method to Reduce Meaning Loss* (No. arXiv:1902.09514). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1902.09514>
- Dong, Q., Li, L., Dai, D., Zheng, C., Ma, J., Li, R., Xia, H., Xu, J., Wu, Z., Chang, B., Sun, X., Li, L., & Sui, Z. (2024). A Survey on In-context Learning. In Y. Al-Onaizan, M. Bansal, & Y.-N. Chen (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing* (pp. 1107–1128). Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.emnlp-main.64>
- Habdank, M., Rodehuts Kors, N., & Koch, R. (2017). Relevancy assessment of tweets using supervised learning techniques: Mining emergency related tweets for automated relevancy classification. *2017 4th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Disaster Management (ICT-DM)*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICT-DM.2017.8275670>
- Hanny, D., Schmidt, S., & Resch, B. (2024). Active Learning for Identifying Disaster-Related Tweets: A Comparison with Keyword Filtering and Generic Fine-Tuning. In K. Arai (Ed.), *Intelligent Systems and Applications* (pp. 126–142). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66428-1_8

- Huang, X., Li, Z., Wang, C., & Ning, H. (2020). Identifying disaster related social media for rapid response: A visual-textual fused CNN architecture. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 13(9), 1017–1039. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17538947.2019.1633425>
- Kaufhold, M.-A., Bayer, M., & Reuter, C. (2020). Rapid relevance classification of social media posts in disasters and emergencies: A system and evaluation featuring active, incremental and online learning. *Information Processing & Management*, 57(1), 102132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2019.102132>
- Liu, H., Tam, D., Muqeeth, M., Mohta, J., Huang, T., Bansal, M., & Raffel, C. (2022). *Few-Shot Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning is Better and Cheaper than In-Context Learning* (No. arXiv:2205.05638). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.05638>
- Madichetty, S., Muthukumarasamy, S., & Jayadev, P. (2021). Multi-modal classification of Twitter data during disasters for humanitarian response. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 12(11), 10223–10237. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020-02791-5>
- Olteanu, A., Vieweg, S., & Castillo, C. (2015). What to Expect When the Unexpected Happens: Social Media Communications Across Crises. *Proceedings of the 18th ACM Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work & Social Computing*, 994–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2675133.2675242>
- Shah, S. A., Yahia, S. B., McBride, K., Jamil, A., & Draheim, D. (2021). Twitter streaming data analytics for disaster alerts. *2021 2nd International Informatics and Software Engineering Conference (IISEC)*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IISEC54230.2021.9672370>
- Tunstall, L., Reimers, N., Jo, U. E. S., Bates, L., Korat, D., Wasserblat, M., & Pereg, O. (2022). *Efficient Few-Shot Learning Without Prompts* (No. arXiv:2209.11055). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2209.11055>
- Wang, F., Zhang, Z., Zhang, X., Wu, Z., Mo, T., Lu, Q., Wang, W., Li, R., Xu, J., Tang, X., He, Q., Ma, Y., Huang, M., & Wang, S. (2024). *A Comprehensive Survey of Small Language Models in the Era of Large Language Models: Techniques, Enhancements, Applications, Collaboration with LLMs, and Trustworthiness* (No. arXiv:2411.03350; Version 1). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2411.03350>
- Wang, L., Yang, N., Huang, X., Yang, L., Majumder, R., & Wei, F. (2024). *Multilingual E5 Text Embeddings: A Technical Report* (No. arXiv:2402.05672). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.05672>
- Wang, Y., Yao, Q., Kwok, J. T., & Ni, L. M. (2020). Generalizing from a Few Examples: A Survey on Few-shot Learning. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 53(3), 63:1-63:34. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3386252>
- Wang, Z., & Ye, X. (2018). Social media analytics for natural disaster management. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 32(1), 49–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2017.1367003>
- Zeff, M. (2024, July 18). OpenAI unveils GPT-4o mini, a smaller and cheaper AI model. *TechCrunch*. <https://techcrunch.com/2024/07/18/openai-unveils-gpt-4o-mini-a-small-ai-model-powering-chatgpt/>